

Micellization of linear alkyl benzene sulphonate and sodium lauryl sulphate in mixed aqueous solution

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Abstract : The micellization behaviour of linear alkyl benzene sulphonate has been studied conductometrically in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate in aqueous solution. The conductance data are used to obtain values of critical micelle concentration, cmc, of mixed surfactant systems of different compositions. The results are interpreted in the light of various possibilities of micelle formation with equilibria between possible surfactant species formed by both the surfactant in mixed system. It has been proved by measuring solubilization of anthracene in mixed surfactant systems and effect of temperature on cmc that the detergency performance of LABS can be enhanced in presence of $\frac{1}{2}$ cmc of sodium lauryl sulphate in aqueous solution.

Keywords : Surfactant, micellization, micelles, solubilization, linear alkyl benzene sulphonate, cmc, conductance.

Introduction

The micelle formation or micellization in solution is an important property of surfactants. It has become a subject of great interest of investigation because surfactants have numerous applications in chemical and industrial processes like spreading over substrate¹, stabilization of emulsion², preparations of cosmetics and pharmaceuticals³, drug delivery⁴, enhanced oil recovery⁵ and detergency⁶. The work has been done on elucidating the various factors like structure of the surfactant, presence of electrolytes or organic additive, temperature etc. that determine the concentration at which micelle formation becomes useful in aqueous media⁷. The effect of additives on micellization and other physico-chemical properties of surfactants are of theoretical as well as industrial interest⁸.

The mixed surfactant systems have been extensively studied⁹ and subject matter reviewed^{10,11}, in recent past due to their application in many industrial and technological formulations. There is a report on mixed micellar system of linear alkyl benzene sulphonate LABS and alpha olefin sulphonate AOS in which it was found that the LABS-AOS (80 : 20) mixed system exhibits superior stain removing ability as compared to LABS alone¹².

It is more useful to investigate the micellization of LABS with other co-surfactant in mixed state in the light

of environmental protection and biodegradable conditions¹³. Keeping in mind the biodegradable tendency and wide industrial application of LABS, an attempt has been made to investigate the mixed micellar system of LABS and sodium lauryl sulphate.

Results and discussion

Critical micelle concentration of LABS :

The cmc values were computed from the plots of [LABS] versus specific conductance. The concentration at which the micellization starts is evident from the change in the slope of the plot and that particular concentration is the cmc of LABS at fixed concentration of SLS in binary mixture of surfactant solution. The cmc values of LABS obtained at different concentration of SLS are given in the bottom of the Table 1.

The obtained values of cmc for LABS show that the presence of co-surfactant SLS affect the micellization in aqueous medium. The cmc values of LABS with increase in [SLS] range 0.002 to 0.012 mol dm⁻³ attains minimum value around 0.0010 mol dm⁻³ at two concentration of SLS 0.004 mol dm⁻³ and 0.008 mol dm⁻³. The cmc value obtained at 0.006 mol dm⁻³ of SLS is higher 0.00140 mol dm⁻³. The decrease in cmc values is believed to be due to the formation of mixed micelle. The monomers of both the surfactants constitute the mixed micelle by re-

Table 1. Specific conductance at different concentrations of LABS and SLS at 298 K

Sl. No.	Specific conductance (m S cm ⁻¹)						
	[SLS] (mol dm ⁻³) 10 ⁴ [LABS] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.012
1.	4.0	0.262	0.312	0.336	0.416	0.512	0.710
2.	6.0	0.406	0.435	0.464	0.540	0.636	0.796
3.	8.0	0.520	0.562	0.600	0.660	0.756	0.880
4.	10.0	0.632	0.675	0.728	0.784	0.880	0.960
5.	12.0	0.744	0.782	0.810	0.908	0.956	1.040
6.	14.0	0.856	0.862	0.872	1.032	1.016	1.120
7.	16.0	0.968	0.960	0.940	1.104	1.080	1.208
8.	18.0	1.080	1.042	1.004	1.144	1.152	1.288
9.	20.0	1.152	1.102	1.068	1.188	1.212	1.360
10.	22.0	1.208	1.170	1.140	1.232	1.280	1.412
11.	24.0	1.264	1.232	1.200	1.272	1.340	1.456
12.	26.0	1.320	1.280	1.264	1.316	1.408	1.508
13.	28.30	1.376	1.352	1.328	1.360	1.472	1.560
14.	30.0	1.436	1.410	1.396	1.400	1.536	1.608
	cmc of LABS (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00185	0.00140	0.0010	0.00145	0.00105	0.00190

ducing the mutual repulsion of the ionic heads, which decreases the work required for micellization. Further increase in surfactant concentration again results the increase in mutual repulsion of ionic head and cmc value attains the higher value. Secondly the hydrophobic character of two surfactants in aqueous solution is greater in comparison to individual surfactant. A quantitative approach towards mixed micelle formation reflects from the experimental decrease in cmc values because the decrease in cmc of LABS is $\frac{1}{2}$ cmc of LABS in water¹⁴, which is obtained at concentration of SLS equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ cmc of SLS in water.

Critical micelle concentration of SLS :

The micellization SLS behaviours of aqueous solution of SLS in presence of surfactant LABS can be deduced from the specific conductivity data given in Table 1. In the [LABS] range below 0.0008 mol dm⁻³, the plots [SLS] versus specific conductance are linear without any break points indicating the presence of monomeric form of both the reactants. At [LABS] 0.001 mol dm⁻³ the cmc obtained for SLS was equal to its cmc in water, which decreased from 0.008 to 0.006 mol dm⁻³ at 0.0012 mol dm⁻³ [LABS]. The conductivity relationship with [SLS] at different concentrations of LABS in the range 0.0014 to 0.0030 mol dm⁻³ is analyzed for linearity relation.

The analysis of data exhibits four linear regions with three transition points. The first point at [SLS] 0.004 mol dm⁻³ corresponds to the mixed monomer formation. Second transition point corresponds to critical aggregation concentration of [SLS] 0.006 mol dm⁻³ at which micellization of mixed micelles takes place. Third transition point corresponds to the mixed micelle saturation where the mixed micelles coexist with the micelles of individual surfactants at [SLS] 0.008 mol dm⁻³. Such transitions have been observed¹⁵ in polymer surfactant systems. At [LABS] 0.0022 mol dm⁻³ and 0.0024 mol dm⁻³, no transition points are obtained. This specific behaviour shows that near and above cmc, the LABS micelle changes the structure of water which leads to the shifting of mixed monolayer \leftrightarrow micelle equilibrium in favour of mixed monolayer and results the postponements of micellization. Such behaviour indicates the synergistic nature of SLS and LABS in mixed monolayer and mixed micelle.

In the present study the results indicates that the addition of SLS tends to promote the formation of LABS micellar in aqueous solution. At two concentrations 0.004 mol dm⁻³ and 0.008 mol dm⁻³ where the SLS have optimum micelle promoting capacity in appropriate ratio with LABS.

At constant temperature the effect of LABS on

micellization of SLS may be more informative for the understanding of mixed surfactant systems. We have observed different equilibriums and transition points [SLS] versus conductivity plots at different [LABS]. These results have shown that for a mixed surfactant solution, there are various possibilities for the micelle formation depending upon the structure and concentration of individual surfactant present in the solution. The various possibilities for micelle formation in case of similarly charged surfactants can be represented by Scheme 1 where n represents the monomeric species of surfactant, S and m represents the micellar state of surfactant, S_{mix} is the micellar structure, the number 1 stands for first surfactant and 2 stands for second surfactant present in mixed micellar system.

The proposed Scheme 1 can be used for predicting the

Scheme 1

various transition and equilibriums obtained in micellization of mixed surfactant system in general.

Solubilization behaviour :

In the present study it was observed that the cmc of LABS attains the minimum value $0.0010 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in mixed surfactant system containing $0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ SLS. The solubilization of anthracene for different [LABS] at constant [SLS] was studied with the help of nephelometer. The results obtained are given in Table 2. It is clear from the experimental data that the solubilization of anthracene takes place at around $0.0010 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration of LABS, which confirm the micellization of LABS at this concentration in presence of $0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ SLS.

Effect of temperature on micellization :

The aim of our work is to study the micellization behaviour of LABS in presence of SLS as co-surfactant. The temperature is an important parameter for micellization. Hence we have obtained the cmc values of

LABS at second temperature at 303 K under similar experimental condition. The data are given in Table 3.

For ionic surfactants the minimum in the cmc temperature curve there appear to be around 298 K¹⁶. Generally increase in temperature causes decreased hydration of the hydrophilic group, which favours micellization. The cmc value of LABS remained constants in presence of $0.006 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ SLS with increase in temperature from 298 K to 303 K. It confirms the phase transformation of single component surfactant in equilibrium with co-surfactant species at this concentration as concluded in the study. The cmc value of LABS in presence of $0.008 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ SLS at 303 K indicates very small decrease in its value. It means the optimum micelle-promoting tendency of SLS for LABS diminishes with increase in temperature but it remains prominent at $0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at half

Table 2. Turbidity value for solubilization of anthracene in LABS and SLS mixed aqueous solution

Sl. No.	[LABS] (mol dm ⁻³)	[SLS] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Anthracene] (mol dm ⁻³)	Turbidity (NTV)
1.	0.0006	0.004	1×10^{-4}	95
2.	0.0008	0.004	1×10^{-4}	81
3.	0.0010	0.004	1×10^{-4}	50
4.	0.0016	0.004	1×10^{-4}	18
5.	0.0020	0.004	1×10^{-4}	10
6.	0.0024	0.004	1×10^{-4}	8

Table 3. cmc values of LABS at 303 K and 298 K

Sl. No.	[SLS] (mol dm ⁻³)	cmc of LABS (mol dm ⁻³)	
		298 K	303 K
1.	0.004	0.00100	0.00110
2.	0.006	0.00145	0.00145
3.	0.008	0.00105	0.00173
4.	0.012	0.00190	0.00200

cmc value of SLS. At higher concentration and temperature, the disruption of the structured water in the surrounding of hydrophobic group which disfavour the micellization.

Finally it can be concluded that detergency performance of LABS can be enhanced at lower concentration by addition of a calculated amount of SLS. The mixed surfactant of LABS with SLS can more cost effective.

Experimental

Deionised water was distilled twice with small quantity of alkaline potassium permanganate. Then water was distilled¹⁷ in a quick fit apparatus with sulphuric acid. The specific conductance of distilled water prepared for the presence study was in the order of $< 2 \times 10^{-6} \Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$. LABS used in the study were obtained in laboratory by sulphonation of linear alkyl benzene (Indian Petrochemical Pvt. Ltd., $C_{10} = 14$, $C_{11} = 32$, $C_{12} = 37$, $C_{13} = 16$ and $C_{14} = 1\%$) having an average molecular weight 343. Sodium lauryl sulphate purchased from S.D. fine Chem. Ltd. The aqueous solutions of LABS and SLS were prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed sample in distilled water.

Surface tension measurements of surfactant solutions were made using a calibrated stalagmometer. No surface tension minimums were found which implies that no surface-active impurities exist in the studied LABS and SLS samples. The techniques employed for the test of impurities was same as reported in literature¹⁸. Thermostatically controlled water bath (Tanco, Kanpur) capable of maintaining the temperature constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ \text{C}$ was used during the all measurements in the study.

Conductivity measurements :

Conductance measurements were taken in a digital conductivity bridge (Elico Pvt. Ltd., Model m-180). A dip type cell of cell constant 0.5 having platinized electrode was used. Single-phase stabilized a.c. mains 50 Hz maintained through out the study. The conductivity bridge was calibrated with potassium chloride solution of known concentration. The error limits in measurements were within $\pm 0.5\%$.

Solubilization measurements :

Solubilization measurements were taken in a nephelometer CL-52D (Elico Pvt. Ltd.). The full range nephelometer (0 to 100 NTU) was used for measurement of turbidity. The errors in reproducible results were within $\pm 2\%$. A tungsten lamp was used as light source. Before the measurements, the instrument was calibrated to adjust set zero control to get the reading zero for distilled

water and for each set, solution of maximum concentration was taken as standard solution for the adjustment of reading 100 with the help of control switch of the instrument. The solubilization behaviour of surfactant was studied in aqueous alcoholic solution of anthracene. The method employed for solubilization study was the same as reported previously¹⁹.

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